

Recommended Practice: Systems of Systems Considerations in the Development of Systems

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Abstract—This paper presents the results of an international collaboration under The Technical Cooperation Program (TTCP), an international organization which collaborates on technical exchange and shared research. Developed under the Systems of Systems Work Stream of the Technical Panel on Systems Engineering and Modernization. Using ISO 15288 as a framework for integrating across the practical experiences of the nations, these recommended practices bring together the collective knowledge from across the US, UK, Canada and Australia on the SoS considerations that need to be addressed at key points in the system development process. The recommended practices are intended for use by systems engineers, program managers and acquisition oversight organizations in government and industry engaged in the development of defense systems in particular, but apply generally across large systems in other domains as well. The recommended practices were developed over a three year process of iterative development with activities in each nation with each iteration to review, apply and refine the information along with open input from industry and academia.

Keywords—system or systems; system acquisition, risk

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's highly interconnected world, most military systems operate as part of an operational deployment which includes multiple systems working in concert to achieve a military mission. While the collection of systems supporting the mission are in fact a system in their own right, only rarely are these 'systems of systems' developed and engineered for the mission. Most defense acquisition processes are focused on the development and procurement of the individual systems. Recognizing this, it is important that when systems are developed or updated once in service, that the operational system of systems environment be considered in the engineering of the systems.

II. RECOMMENDED PRACTICES GUIDE

A. Background

The US, UK, Canada, Australia and New Zealand are the partner nations in The Technical Cooperation Program (TTCP),

an "international organization that collaborates in defense scientific and technical information exchange; program harmonization and alignment; and shared research activities for the five nations." [1] The TTCP Technical Panel 4 (TP-4): "Systems Engineering for Defence Modernization" of the Joint Systems Analysis (JSA) Group with representatives from the US, UK, Canada, and Australia addresses cross-cutting issues in systems engineering and development. For the past five years, this panel has hosted a workstream focused on SoS. The guide to recommended practices for SoS considerations in system development [2] discussed in this paper is a product of this workstream.

A. Motivation

Defense capabilities depend on the effective operation of complex systems of systems, making it particularly important that the development of the constituent systems consider the larger systems of systems environments where the systems will be deployed and operated be addressed effectively throughout the system development. For example, assessment of early system concepts to address capability gaps needs to be done with a clear understanding of the current and projected system support to the capability, and an appreciation of the way a new system would fit into this systems of systems as well as any changes which might be needed in the other systems to effectively employ a new system development toward improved capability. As the development continues, there are key technical considerations to ensure that interfaces and dependencies are addressed in the design and that these considerations match the ongoing developments of the other systems supporting the same capability. These lead to management and funding considerations, which if addressed early can be incorporated into the overall planning for the new systems as well as the other related systems.

B. Structure of the Guide

The recommended practices are presented as a series of extended tables, one for each of the selected review points in the system development process, as shown in Figure 1. ISO 15288 was used as the framework for the review points since

it provides a common reference for the particular engineering processes which are in place in each of the nations.

Fig 1. Key Review Points for SoS Considerations

The review points are logical points in the process to address SoS considerations. In some nations, these are aligned to formal technical reviews, but they are considered appropriate points to address SoS considerations whether or not formal system technical reviews are conducted at these points. In-Service reviews are conducted after the system has been fielded and is in operation and support. The in-service review addresses how well the system is delivering the capability to the user and how well the system is sustained and positioned to meet future operational scenarios, recognizing the changes which may have taken place since the system was fielded.

The current approach to assess a system’s maturity from a system perspective is offered as context for the introduction of the SoS considerations, which are recommended to be addressed for each review point. This information is presented in the form of an extended table for each review point as shown in figure 2.

The screenshot shows a template for a review point table. At the top, there is a header with 'Review Point: Review Name' and a green arrow pointing to a stage box (Exploratory, Conceptual, Development, Production, Utilization/Support). Below this are several sections: 'State of Program at this Review Point', 'Information Available at this Review Point', 'System Issues at this Review Point', 'Questions', 'SoS issues impacting the System' (which includes a table with columns: Area, Questions, Benefits, Risks, Evidence/Metrics, Potential Actions/Mitigations), and 'SoS Supporting Technical Base'.

Fig 2. Recommended Practices Table Illustrated

C. Audience and Use Concept

The tables are structured by review point based on the notion that they will be used by systems engineers, program managers, and acquisition oversight organizations in government and industry as a reference for their systems development activities at each review point. They are intended for use in the development of defense systems in particular, but they may apply more generally across large

systems in other domains as well. It is expected that national acquisition agencies will incorporate these SoS considerations into their current system-focused reviews and management processes. To the degree possible, the guide adopts definitions from the SE Body of Knowledge (SEBoK), thus using a broad SE context that can be adapted to a variety of user environments.

III. SoS CONSIDERATIONS

SoS considerations in the guide fall into four categories: capability, technical, management and cost. Each consideration is presented in the form of a question which addresses whether the system has factored a particular consideration into the system development at that point. In some cases, questions apply to multiple review points, indicating the importance to monitor changes to those questions across the whole life-cycle in order to reduce risks or avoid significant additional costs. For each question, the table presents the benefits of addressing the consideration and the risks of failing to do so. It also identifies the type of information or artifacts that provide the information needed to address the question and possible mitigating actions when the questions cannot be satisfactorily addressed. Each table also includes a description of the type of information which would ideally be available to the system engineer about the system and larger SoS. It would provide the technical base for addressing the questions posed at that point in the system’s development. This SoS technical base is important since it ties the decisions about a particular system to the technical data about the larger SoS.

A. Capability Considerations

New systems and system upgrades are typically driven by the need for a user capability (that is, the ability to perform a function, task, or action [SEBoK 1.2]).

Typically in defense acquisition, a user capability gap has been identified and the system acquisition focuses on filling that gap. Consequently, right from the earliest point in a system development, an understanding of the role of a new system in supporting the capability is a key concern, particularly understanding how the system is envisioned to function in the operational context including the constraints that context places on the system and the relationships, interfaces and dependencies with other systems supporting the capability.

As the system’s development continues, these considerations remain important, particularly when changes may have occurred in the operational context or in the other systems supporting the capability. It is also imperative that system dependencies are successfully communicated to the other systems so that any changes, or trade-offs, can be identified and addressed in the system concept, alternatives, requirements and eventually design. Dependencies can go in both directions. To achieve a capability with a new system, it may require changes in other systems in the SoS. Understanding this early and factoring it into planning process can be the key to successful deliver both the system and the capability it enables.

B. Technical Considerations

As system concepts are explored and alternative approaches are evaluated, it is important to consider external stakeholders or external systems/infrastructure which are affected. This includes both systems/services on which the new or upgraded system depends; and systems/services that depend on the new or upgraded system. Once these have been identified it is important to assess the ability to influence resource changes in associated systems, infrastructure, or non-material factors. In addition it is important to identify if constraints on the system are imposed by its SoS context and to consider these in selecting the system solution. This includes physical (e.g. size, weight, cooling, power limits, operational environments) and electronic requirements (e.g. signature, interference, etc.) as well as requirements associated with information exchange and management (e.g. network, bandwidth, information needs, etc.), safety, security and information assurance.

As the system moves into requirements definition and design, the technical consideration play a larger role. What requirements are derived from the SoS dependencies? How are SoS-derived technical requirements used in technical planning? How are they used to define interfaces and data sharing agreements? For considerations which involve interactions with other systems (e.g. interfaces, new or changed functionality in other systems), how are the specifications negotiated with the others involved? How are SoS-derived technical requirements and resulting interfaces addressed in the system design?

C. Management Considerations

Technical management issues come into play as the design is finalized. For considerations which involve interactions with other systems (e.g. interfaces, new or changed functionality in other systems) design features may need to be negotiated with the “owners” of the other systems involved. Forecasting may need to be undertaken to establish what future interfaces are needed to support an evolving SoS.

SoS dependencies need to be addressed in the management of the acquisition program, with explicit mechanisms to identify, define and control dependencies and interfaces and approaches to manage these across systems. There may be complementary systems critical to the success of the proposed system. Who are responsible for these systems and do they acknowledge the dependency? There may be impacts on external systems that need to be addressed to meet the capability needs once the new system or system upgrade is implemented.

If the system supports one or more acknowledged or directed SoS, it is important that management arrangements have been established with the organization responsible for the SoS(s) which this acquisition program supports. In the best case, these have been formalized through MOUs or MOAs and the key provisions been implemented, such as how additional funding of interface adjustments might be addressed. If there is no acknowledged SoS management, then other management arrangements will need to be implemented with the “owners” of other systems which impact this system. The

customer(s) of the system will also need to be informed of these arrangements as trade-offs may need to be made that improve the SoS capability while reducing the system performance. These are key questions for systems in design and development stages.

D. Cost and Schedule Considerations

Finally, SoS related cost and schedule considerations need to be addressed as early in the system’s development as possible. This includes identifying costs and schedules associated with external systems, and including these in cost and schedule estimates for these external systems. SoS-related costs and schedule considerations include planning, and integration and tests. Finally, mechanisms need to be in place to monitor progress in the areas of cross-system dependencies for prompt identification of any changes or delays which could mean added cost and time. Plans need to be formulated to accommodate these if necessary.

E. SoS Technical Base

SoS supporting technical data, available starting early in the system’s development, includes established end-to-end capability objectives, performance metrics and current performance data, an understanding of the systems currently supporting the SoS under the present concept of operations, as well as the overall SoS technical baseline. Ideally an SoS architecture would be employed as the framework for understanding how the system will support the capability (including functionality, performance, interfaces, data exchanges etc.) and interdependencies among systems. As well, non-material aspects of the supporting capability should be fully evaluated and assessed. The SoS artifacts (such as Capability Objectives, Concept of Operation, SoS Architecture, Technical Baselines, Performance Measures and Methods, Agreements etc [3]) would be part of preliminary and formal system design reviews, providing a mechanism for monitoring changes of any SoS considerations for this system thus preventing loss of previous considerations and assumptions. They provide a strong technical basis for system design decisions.

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